

RE4GREEN

Delphi Round 1: Feedback Report for Participants

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Executive summary

Achieving a just green transition in Europe, as envisaged in the European Green Deal, requires training across the research and innovation sectors on how to adequately consider environmental, climate and broader justice considerations in research and innovation activities. Competence profiles can help ensure all actors have the skills, knowledge, attitudes and abilities to contribute to the green transition.

As an expert who provides education for researchers and innovators on environmental and justice issues, we invited you to participate in a Delphi survey to identify areas of agreement amongst experts on items to include in a competence profile for environmentally aware research and innovation. In this report, we present the results from the first round of the Delphi survey.

Twenty-one experts from across Europe and beyond participated in the Delphi survey.

In the first section, we asked you what sustainability looks like in the context of responsible research and innovation. Across all experts, definitions described sustainability as normative, guided by ethical principles, and taking a long-term approach. Some respondents considered sustainability as maintaining social and environmental systems within certain boundaries, whereas others stated that sustainability is aimed at an idealised future state. Experts affirmed that sustainability required the inclusion of multiple perspectives and could be achieved only through multi-disciplinarity and multi-sectoral cooperation. Experts emphasized that sustainability requires a paradigm shift in the conduct of research and innovation, reflects a broader conception of progress, and is associated with specific approaches and practices. Some experts however also voiced critiques of the term, stating that in use it has become a *'catch-all'*, *'empty'*, *'buzzword'* due to its *'globalisation'*.

In the second section we asked your agreement on items to include in the competence profile which were developed based on insights derived from in-depth interviews with environmental education and research integrity specialists. The items were structured to reflect the EU GreenComp framework, which defines sustainability as "prioritising the needs of all life forms and of the planet by ensuring that human activity does not exceed planetary boundaries" (Bianchi et al 2022). Experts agreed on 39 competency items, which will now be used to structure the development of training materials for researchers and innovators. No agreement was reached on nine competency items. These have been refined based on expert feedback and will be included in the Delphi survey second round.

Section 1 – ‘What does sustainability look like in the context of responsible research and innovation?’

The Delphi survey started with an open question: ‘What does sustainability look like in the context of responsible research and innovation?’ In summary, according to the respondents:

Sustainability is **normative** – *‘it’s a normative project’, ‘necessary structural change’, ‘largely used as a synonym for “better”.*

Sustainability is **guided by ethical principles** such as *‘intersectionality, justice, dignity, respect, fairness, honesty, and care’, ‘equal and just’, ‘inclusive, transparent, and responsive to societal needs’, ‘a tripartite value consisting of intragenerational justice, intergenerational justice, and care for nature’.*

Sustainability involves having a **long-term approach** – *‘building consideration for the future’, ‘espouses a long-termism view’, ‘looking at the extended life cycle of research’, ‘thinks about future generations (Seventh Generation Principle)’, ‘ensuring the actions serve both present and future generations [...] and long-term oriented’.*

Some respondents described sustainability as **staying within certain boundaries** – *‘intended as the capacity to leave the future generations with at least the same options we have had’, ‘research and innovation should be aimed at the common good within planetary boundaries’* - whereas others described sustainability as **achieving an idealised future state** – *‘sustainability really refers to some kind of state that is not what we have now’, ‘a preferred future state of human-nature interaction’, ‘a more harmonious development of humanity as a goal’*

Sustainability requires the inclusion of **multiple perspectives** – *‘is an interdisciplinary and intersectoral knowledge and practice exercise’, ‘creating intergenerational and inclusive solutions’, ‘engaging diverse actors’, ‘plurality, heterogenous social landscape’.* As well as **multidisciplinary and involving multi-sectoral cooperation** – *‘emphasizes the need for multidisciplinary (environmental, social, economic, ethical, etc.) and systemic approaches to knowledge, research and innovation’*

Sustainability requires **a paradigm shift in the conduct of research and innovation**, described broadly in terms of new ways of doing research and innovation – *‘Epistemologically, working aiming at contributing to sustainability means to rethink how we have been doing things’, ‘It embodies a paradigm shift towards an epistemic and ethical reimagining of knowledge production’* or in terms of the broad areas which require further attention or approaches/methodologies which can bring about

the desired shift in practice - '*build consideration for the future into their professional and personal activities linking social, environmental, and climate goals for enacting necessary structural change*', '*This approach integrates environmental, social, and cultural dimensions, fostering an inclusive and decolonial methodology that acknowledges diverse ways of knowing*', '*adopting a socio-eco-technical perspective and ethical reflection on innovation and research, avoiding a solely technological view on innovation that is only oriented towards economic growth*'.

Some respondents also highlighted **specific approaches and practices that support sustainability in research and innovation** - '*following community-based open science, such as CARE and FAIR principles in open science and indigenous data governance (among others) or Citizen Science to help Citizens' empowerment, and non-anthropocentric perspectives. It has developed research designs, and models: Life cycle assessment (LCA), DPRSIR and Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) model, which can be used for environmental standards to collect, analysis, assess, and reporting of data*', '*includes minimizing the environmental footprint of activities (e.g. by reducing travel, energy consumption, and designing products (e.g. AI technologies), with the lowest possible environmental impact*'.

Sustainability ultimately **reflects a broader conception of progress** - '*ensuring that progress supports long-term ecological balance, social equity, and resilient economies*' - which values nature and other species - '*consider interpersonal and interspecies relationships*', '*intrinsicity of nature*'.

Some respondents were **critical of the term sustainability**, considering that in use it has become a '*catch-all*', '*empty*', '*buzzword*' due to its 'globalisation'. There was also recognition that the term sustainability has **different interpretations** 'depending on the individual knowledge, ethical principles and positions supported (e.g., strong or weak sustainability)'. Specific **barriers to sustainability** were also mentioned '*Proprietary technology particularly can pose a problem since it is not as fixable/replaceable*'.

Table 1. Expert responses to the open question 'What does sustainability look like in the context of responsible research and innovation'

For me, a research and innovation project/programmer is ABOUT sustainability if: the research contributes to identifying, developing, or disseminating knowledge, tools, or other research outputs, which are useful for advancing towards "sustainability" (however defined), either in generally, or
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<p>within the specific scope of the research project. It's about providing actionable knowledge, its a normative project.</p>
<p>The label of sustainability is increasingly coming under criticism. The globalisation of the term is often thought to have led to its heuristic devaluation, i.e. a catch-all label, that in the end becomes ideationally empty. What sustainability should mean in the context of research and innovation, is the production of knowledge which espouses a long-termist view, i.e. knowledge that helps practitioners and citizens build consideration for the future into their professional and personal activities linking social, environmental, and climate goals for enacting necessary structural change.</p>
<p>Sustainability means looking at the extended life cycle of research. This includes the materials needed for tools and instrumentation, livability of staff and researchers, energy consumption, disposal, and reuse. Proprietary technology particularly can pose a problem since it is not as fixable/replaceable. A good alternative example can be found in Max Liboiron's CLEAR Lab using a homemade Baby Legs.</p>
<p>I refer to it as based on the "People, Planet, and Prosperity" idea, that I prefer to the narrative on social, environmental, and economic, as the latter narrow down research areas too much. Sustainability - intended as the capacity to leave the future generations with at least the same options we have had - is an interdisciplinary and intersectoral knowledge and practice exercise (intersectoral for me is more academia and NGOs/social movements than academia and companies). Epistemologically, working aiming at contributing to sustainability means to rethink how we have been doing things.</p>
<p>It means responding to current challenges or needs without putting in risk the current and future environmental and societal contexts or capacities by creating intergenerational and inclusive solutions following community-based open science, such as CARE and FAIR principles in open science and indigenous data governance (among others) or Citizen Science to help Citizens' empowerment, and non-anthropocentric perspectives.</p>
<p>For me its all about innovation. This should involve environmentally responsible, socially inclusive, and economically viable, ensuring that progress supports long-term ecological balance, social equity, and resilient economies</p>
<p>Ethical (guided by : intersectionality, justice, dignity, respect, fairness, honesty, and care ('the seven principles'), consider interpersonal and interspecies relationships, thinks about future generations (Seventh Generation Principle).</p>
<p>sustainability is an important and often overarching component in research and innovation</p>
<p>Dominantly, sustainability represents a technocratic vision of maintaining the status quo. In research, sustainability is largely used as a synonym for "better" (as in sustainable agriculture, or sustainable consumption). Even though it suggests a positive alternative state, sustainability really refers to some kind of state that is not what we have now.</p>
<p>I have no idea. The wording is vague. Are you asking about research about sustainability, or sustainable researching methods?</p>
<p>Sustainability in research and innovation, from my perspective, transcends the mere development of eco-friendly technologies or practices. It embodies a paradigm shift towards an epistemic and ethical reimagining of knowledge production. This approach integrates environmental, social, and cultural dimensions, fostering an inclusive and decolonial methodology that acknowledges diverse ways of knowing. Therefore, sustainability in research and innovation is not solely about mitigating environmental impacts but about cultivating a transformative, culturally responsive, and ethically grounded approach</p>
<p>Anticipating trends and impacts, engaging diverse actors, and ensuring the actions serve both present and future generations. Engaging with perceptions, thinking, practices and organisational structures etc. that are regenerative, inclusive, and long-term oriented.</p>
<p>relevant in the future</p>
<p>In my opinion, sustainability is a complex concept that emphasizes the need for multidisciplinary (environmental, social, economic, ethical, etc.) and systemic approaches to knowledge, research and</p>

<p>innovation. It can have different interpretations in everyday practices, depending on the individual knowledge, ethical principles and positions supported (e.g., strong or weak sustainability).</p>
<p>In addition to being a flexible buzzword, it connotes attention to caring for the environment and social/cultural values in the long-term.</p>
<p>As in other contexts, sustainability in research and innovation means a preferred future state of human-nature interaction, where human activities do not threaten other life on earth but instead ensure equal and just use of natural resources. Research and innovation ought to promote such activities that help reaching a more sustainable state. This means considering sustainability and ethics in both research topics and practices, as well as in required infrastructure, materials, and interaction with research participants (humans and non-humans).</p>
<p>From the perspective of research and innovation, in my reading, sustainability can be a goal and/or an approach. I think of the technological and social aspects that lead to a more harmonious development of humanity as a goal. And if we think in terms of approach, we mean research and innovation that is carried out in a socially, economically and environmentally sustainable way.</p>
<p>Sustainability encompasses economic, environmental, and social concepts. It has developed research designs, and models: Life cycle assessment (LCA), DPRSIR and Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) model, which can be used for environmental standards to collect, analysis, assess, and reporting of data. Also, sustainability in innovation refers to the development of new products or services that make a positive contribution to sustainability. For example, Serbian company has developed a product upon innovative technology, a Strawberry Tree, the first public solar battery charger for mobile devices</p>
<p>Sustainability in R&I means the responsible use of resources. This includes minimizing the environmental footprint of activities (e.g. by reducing travel, energy consumption, and designing products (e.g. AI technologies), with the lowest possible environmental impact. Sustainability also includes ensuring the long-term relevance of R&I by addressing global challenges like climate change and social inequality. It should incorporate ethical practices, open science principles, and a consideration of systemic impact to ensure that R&I is inclusive, transparent, and responsive to societal needs.</p>
<p>My/Our understanding of sustainability is based on the three pillar model of sustainability as social, economic and environmental sustainability. That means, when people conduct research and innovation, they should be aware of these dimensions in advance. It also means adopting a socio-eco-technical perspective and ethical reflection on innovation and research, avoiding a solely technological view on innovation that is only oriented towards economic growth. Instead, research and innovation should be aimed at the common good within planetary boundaries.</p>
<p>Sustainability is a normative concept that has environmental and social dimensions. While there are many definitions, in the context of research and innovation, it can be seen as a tripartite value consisting of intragenerational justice, intergenerational justice, and care for nature (Van de Poel, 2017). With this conceptualization, it is possible to capture both environmental and social dimensions of this notion and emphasize several important premises: i) temporality, considerations of future generations, ii) plurality, heterogenous social landscape, and iii) intrinsicality of nature.</p>

Section 2 - Agreement and disagreement on draft competence items

Agreement on competency items (consensus)

Experts were then asked to state their level of agreement on a 5-point Likert scale on draft competence items for fostering environmentally aware research and innovation. Consensus was predefined as having been achieved if greater 69% of respondents agreed/strongly agreed to an item.

Greater than 69% agreement was achieved on 39 competency items, in fact even higher consensus thresholds (greater than 79%) were achieved on 26 items (Table 2).

Table 2. Competency items for which agreement was achieved amongst experts.

	% agree or strongly agree
1. Embodying Sustainability Values	
1.1 Valuing sustainability	
Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge diverse perspectives and values concerning environmental and climate justice in the context of research and innovation.	85,7
Researchers and innovators should... reflect on how personal values and perspectives regarding the environment influence decisions and actions taken during the research process.	95,2
Researchers and innovators should... consider reducing environmental harms and increasing environmental benefits to be a professional responsibility in research and innovation.	90,5
Researchers and innovators should... apply the do no (significant) harm principle and precautionary principle in relation to research and innovation.	85,7
1.2 Supporting fairness	

Researchers and innovators should... recognize the disproportionate impact of the planetary crisis on and within different communities due to coloniality and systemic injustice.	85,7
Researchers and innovators should... consider the implications of global and local justice perspectives on research methodologies, priorities, and outcomes.	81,0
Researchers and innovators should... support equity and justice for present and future generations in research and innovation proposals.	90,5
1.3 Promoting nature	
Researchers and innovators should... acknowledge that research and innovation are embedded in, and can cause significant harm to, ecological systems.	81,0
Researchers and innovators should... perceive the needs and rights of other (non-human) species and of nature itself as a fundamental aspect of research ethics.	76,2
Researchers and innovators should... practice care and respect towards the environment and other species when designing a research or innovation project.	90,5
2. Embracing Complexity	
2.1 Systems thinking	
Researchers and innovators should... be aware that the complexity of environmental, climate and sustainability challenges can be emotionally impactful.	81,0
Researchers and innovators should... use systems thinking to determine the environmental consequences (including unintended consequences) of research and innovation activities.	76,2

2.2 Critical thinking	
Researchers and innovators should... recognize potential trade-offs between competing priorities (people, planet, profit) in research and innovation.	71,4
Researchers and innovators should... evaluate the validity of information sources regarding environmental problems and potential solutions (e.g. technological solutions).	90,5
Researchers and innovators should... align project aims with alternative approaches towards growth and consumption which are informed by more sustainable and just economic models.	71,4
Researchers and innovators should... build in opportunities for critical reflection throughout research and innovation projects to ensure continuous alignment with sustainability principles.	81,0
2.3 Problem framing	

Researchers and innovators should... identify common challenges, risks, and uncertainties related to the environmental and climate impacts of research and innovation activities in your field.	81,0
Researchers and innovators should... map out all stakeholders affected by a research and innovation project – including communities, industries, policymakers, and ecosystems.	85,7
Researchers and innovators should... openly and transparently communicate potential benefits and risks of a project to the environment, climate, and affected communities.	85,7
3. Envisioning Sustainable Futures	
3.1 Futures literacy	
Researchers and innovators should... envision sustainable outcomes and identify possible actions, innovations, and/or policies that would support these outcomes.	76,2
Researchers and innovators should... anticipate ethical concerns of emerging technologies and their environmental and climate impacts.	95,2
Researchers and innovators should... employ techniques for futures thinking, such as scenario development or speculative design, in relation to a planned research or innovation project.	71,4
Researchers and innovators should... align immediate research and innovation efforts with long-term sustainability visions, adaptively balancing present needs and long-term sustainability objectives.	76,2
3.2 Adaptability	
Researchers and innovators should... consider emerging evidence on environmental harms caused by research and innovation, including the cumulative harms of all research and innovation activities.	81,0
Researchers and innovators should... monitor progress toward envisioned futures and adjust strategies based on new insights or changing circumstances.	71,4
Researchers and innovators should... mitigate against the environmental impact of research and innovation by considering alternate approaches (e.g., frugal innovation).	81,0

Researchers and innovators should... participate in continuous learning activities to ensure professional skills are applicable to changing ecological and social circumstances.	90,5
3.3 Exploratory thinking	
Researchers and innovators should... understand how alternative disciplinary and role-specific perspectives can complement one another.	90,5
Researchers and innovators should... respect local and traditional knowledges and methods to address sustainability in research and innovation.	100
Researchers and innovators should... engage with key ethical debates regarding the environmental and climate impacts of a research and innovation project.	81,0
4. Acting for sustainability	
4.1 Political action	
Researchers and innovators should... recognise that sustainable approaches to research and innovation exist within the context of wider political systems.	85,7
Researchers and innovators should... identify research and innovation priorities which can contribute to a just transition towards a sustainable society.	76,2
Researchers and innovators should... be aware of the access to knowledge, networks and platforms that your role entails, and use this to promote environmentally and socially responsible action.	76,2
Researchers and innovators should... strategically engage in policy dialogue and participatory processes for green initiatives as part of the research methodology or innovation cycle, when appropriate.	76,2
4.2 Collective action	
Researchers and innovators should... remember the importance of teamwork and collective action in tackling environmental (including climate) issues.	90,5

Researchers and innovators should... demonstrate a capacity for accessible and collaborative work, for example through open science and FAIR data practices.	85,7
Researchers and innovators should... collaborate with multiple actors (such as policy makers and local communities) to shape sustainable approaches to research and innovation.	71,4
4.3 Individual Initiative	
Researchers and innovators should... recognise that everyone has a role to play in fostering sustainable approaches to research and innovation.	71,4
Researchers and innovators should... be accountable for the environmental and social impacts of professional activities and take corrective actions where needed.	90,5

Disagreement on competence items (dissensus)

No agreement was reached on nine competency items (Table 3)

Table 3. Competency items for which no agreement (predefined as >69% agree or strongly agree) was achieved amongst experts

	% agree or strongly agree	% neutral	% disagree or strongly disagree
1. Embodying Sustainability Values			
1.2 Supporting fairness			
Researchers and innovators should... conduct all research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice in the green transition.	61,9	28,6	9,5
1.3 Promoting nature			
Researchers and innovators should... devise evidence-based strategies for improving ecosystem health as part of research and innovation.	61,9	33,3	4,8
2. Embracing Complexity			
2.1 Systems thinking			

Researchers and innovators should... define sustainability in research and innovation as a 'wicked problem' with multiple interdependent factors.	61,9	19,0	19,0
Researchers and innovators should... recognize the influence of time, space and context on the sustainability of research and innovation activities.	66,7	23,8	9,5
2.3 Problem framing			

Researchers and innovators should... engage multiple stakeholders from the outset and incorporate their perspectives and priorities on environmental issues.	66,7	19,0	14,3
3.3 Exploratory thinking			
Researchers and innovators should... plan every step of a research and innovation project with sustainability principles in mind, through a process of creative and systematic inquiry (for example using techniques from design thinking and ethics by design).	66,7	23,8	9,5
4. Acting for sustainability			
4.2 Collective action			
Researchers and innovators should... participate in environmental and climate-positive initiatives within your research field.	61,9	28,6	9,5
4.3 Individual Initiative			
Researchers and innovators should... appreciate how personal research goals can contribute to global sustainability objectives, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).	61,9	28,6	9,5

<p>Researchers and innovators should... act as a green role model for other researchers and collaborators by applying sustainability competences in all areas of research and innovation including methodology, materials selection, and project goals.</p>	<p>57,1</p>	<p>33,3</p>	<p>9,5</p>
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Each of these nine items are presented below (under their original domain and with their original numbering) together with the proportion of respondents who agreed/strongly agreed, were neutral, or disagreed/strongly disagreed and respondents' rationales for their responses (if given). Based on respondents' comments, these competency items have been adjusted and will be submitted to experts to rate again in round two of the Delphi survey.

Embodying Sustainability Values

Original item

1.2 Supporting fairness		
Researchers and innovators should... conduct all research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice in the green transition.		
Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]	Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]	Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]
61,9	28,6	9,5
<p>Some respondents were in agreement with the item, but did not consider it to apply to all research.</p> <p><i>"I agree to the extent that the research in question is relevant to contributing towards those things."</i></p> <p><i>"Generally, I strongly agree with this, but acknowledge there may be exceptions."</i></p>	<p>Some respondents who were in favour of social and environmental justice responded neutrally to the item due to perceived lack of attention to justice in Green Transition policy and the perceived tensions created by the coupling of the Green and the Digital Transitions.</p> <p><i>"The green transition is a double edge sword - now, in the shape of the concept of the "twin transition", it is basically a way of removing</i></p>	<p>One respondent disagreed with the item because it did not apply to all research.</p> <p><i>"This is not relevant for ALL kinds of R&I, especially not research, and in particular since those contributions cannot always be anticipated. I agree with the content of the</i></p>

"I believe this would be a powerful way to connect research to real-world challenges and make research and innovation meaningful in everyone's lives. However, I'm not sure this approach can be applied equally across all fields."

Others considered social and environmental justice as essential for achieving the green transition.

"In a context of heightened injustice, this is a moral imperative for researchers. It has been proven though multiple works that without social acceptability (read improving on current injustices) the green transition would face too much pushback to be successful. It is also clear that researchers are also citizens who should feel a moral imperative to contribute to a better society. A better society is not possible without addressing the many facets of climate action."

"Social and environmental dimensions of sustainability go hand in hand"

"There is no justice if we are not able to take together the social and the economical perspectives."

justice from the picture. My feeling is that some decision makers sees it as a way of replacing the conversation on sustainability, that entails more stuff than just green and digital. Therefore, I am in doubt on how to deal with that."

"The Green transition carries with it a set of political framing that are contested. Justice is a powerful frame that I have hard time arguing against it being at the center of a transformative sustainability paradigm. So I wouldn't equate the GT and justice."

"Social justice may be too divorced from the Green transition. We should emphasize harm reduction over a debatable term like "justice."

One respondent responded neutrally because it is not always possible to know how research can further justice goals.

"It is not always possible to identify these (e.g. basic research) and there are often risks to a research project that may raise concerns. For example, the results can be used for very good and for very bad."

statement but I strongly object to its generality"

One respondent strongly disagreed that justice commitments should be tied to the Green Transition policies, and therefore disagreed with the item.

"I don't think competencies should be tight to any political targets, especially when green transition only refer to climate issues and excludes nature loss."

Others described social and environmental responsibilities as equally important but distinct competence items or without a common understanding

"This competence is essential, but the statement would benefit from distinguishing social and environmental responsibility more clearly. While both are integral to the green transition, they involve different forms of knowledge, ethical considerations, and stakeholder engagement. Social justice involves addressing inequality, inclusion, and community impact, while environmental justice focuses on ecosystems, climate resilience, and interspecies ethics. Lumping them together risks oversimplifying the complexity of each."

"Sound good, but as sustainability, green transitions, etc. are normatively contested concepts, we need more ethical discourse and democratic debates on how to contribute to social and environmental justice in the green transition."

One respondent agreed with the item, but – like some of the comments of those who responded neutrally or in disagreement with the item – was critical of the justice commitments in Green Transition policies.

"I partly agree with this statement because the green transition is problematic in itself, as it is rooted in colonial legacies. It often follows similar extractivist patterns as fossil-fuel-based energy, so I would carefully place it in the same sentence with environmental and social justice."

Proposed item wording change

1.2 Supporting fairness

Conduct ~~all~~ research and innovation activities in a way that contributes to both social and environmental justice ~~in the green transition.~~

Original item

1.3 Promoting nature

Researchers and innovators should... devise evidence-based strategies for improving ecosystem health as part of research and innovation.

<p>Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>
<p>61,9</p>	<p>33,3</p>	<p>4,8</p>
<p>Some respondents agreed with the item because it reflects a move away from a simplistic 'do no harm' approach, toward an understanding of the inter-relatedness of ecosystem and human health and active attempts to improve ecosystem health through research decisions.</p> <p><i>"We need to move towards nature restoration, and be more ambitious than simply "preventing further harm".</i></p>	<p>Some respondents were neutral because they did not consider the item to be applicable for all types of research.</p> <p><i>"Evidence is sometimes not available."</i></p> <p><i>"Sounds good, but not applicable to all research."</i></p> <p><i>"I have doubts about the whole "evidence-based" narrative, that</i></p>	<p>One respondent disagreed with the item because they considered the evidence about what improves ecosystem health to be too uncertain.</p> <p><i>"I think that there is too much uncertainty on what creates ecosystem health here. There is a lot of sustainability research that claims evidence based</i></p>

"Ecosystem health is intrinsically linked to human health, climate resilience, and long-term sustainability. Including the competence to devise evidence-based strategies for improving ecosystem health ensures that researchers and innovators do not only avoid harm but also contribute positively to planetary well-being. This reflects the shift from "do no harm" to a regenerative approach in research ethics and aligns with the principles of planetary health and nature-based solutions."

"Ultimately caring for the wider human health"

"We need to use our knowledge to improve not only our quality of life or our health but also the ecosystems health; these aspects are all strictly interconnected."

One respondent agreed, but wanted to go further and include framing the interconnectedness in terms of ecosystem services.

excludes, for example, non-Western epistemologies."

advice for ecosystem health based on abstract modelling exercises based on assumptions about the world that hopefully can be changed."

"This is also relevant. Would add ecosystem services somehow also into this one to underline the need to understand, that our actions that harm ecosystems will finally cause harm to ourselves."

Another respondent stated that the item is important because an understanding and attention to interconnectedness is currently lacking.

"I believe we are lagging behind on this point, which makes it all the more necessary to address it now."

Proposed item wording change

1.3 Promoting nature

Devise **evidence-based** strategies for improving ecosystem health **based on best available evidence** as part of research and innovation.

2. Embracing Complexity

Original item

2.1 Systems thinking

Researchers and innovators should... define sustainability in research and innovation as a 'wicked problem' with multiple interdependent factors.

<p>Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>
61,9	19,0	19,0
<p>A wicked problem is a social or cultural issue that is difficult or impossible to solve due to its complex, interconnected, and often contradictory nature. These problems lack a clear definition, a single "correct" solution, and often involve multiple stakeholders with conflicting interests.</p> <p>Some researchers fully agreed with this framing:</p>		<p>Two respondents had a strong dislike of the term 'wicked problem'</p> <p><i>"Kind of an empty concept at this moment that hides more than it reveals. I eye roll every time I hear it. We should be pushing to reveal a set of known underlying drivers of</i></p>

"Yes - "wicked" is super complex, difficult to frame and one embedding different visions, implying there are few, if any, easy fixes."

"Yes, sustainability is a "wicked problem" because it involves multifaced and interconnected perspectives, related not only to knowledge but also to ethical positions and principles. For this, also some conflicts could emerge."

"This topic has so many layers of complexity which makes it difficult to tackle."

"Wicked problems cannot always be dealt with in this way, but it can be strived for."

"Yes, it could be a useful research strategy among others."

Other respondents, even though they agreed with the perspective, considered it difficult – considering the organization of academia - to approach sustainability in such an interdisciplinary way.

environmental problems rooted in unregulated markets, unequal wealth distribution, the legacies of colonialism, ideologies of progress, corporate consolidation etc."

"Too slang-y. Sounds unprofessional."

Whereas another wanted sustainability to be considered a value researchers should act upon rather than a problem to solve.

"In my view, we should not see sustainability as a problem but rather as a value that can be operationalized to evaluate research and innovation practice."

"I think this is true and a useful way to frame the problem, though i'd be cautious about saying that researchers HAVE to engage with it in that way"

"This can be a promising strategy, but I have several reservations: academia is built in siloed ways with few rigorous methods for interdisciplinarity, the idea that an engineer would try to tackle philosophical and/or social issues in the same research project makes my skin crawl. If the wicked problem lens is helpful, great, if it leads to conclusions of poor quality, then it should not be a priority. This is especially the case when producing highly specialized applied research. However, we still need researchers able to piece the puzzle back together."

Still others thought that the item could go further – specifying the need for attention to multiple perspectives and values on the potential solutions to wicked problems or for more responsive remedial actions.

"The importance of defining not just wicked problems but "remedial" actions in complex systems/networks that link institutions, social networks, non-human networks and so on as well as their inter- and intra- connections. For example: Morton, Lois & Eigenbrode, Sanford & Martin, Timothy. (2015).

Architectures of adaptive integration in large collaborative projects. ECOLOGY AND SOCIETY"

"Yes, but I would add that also the solutions should be seen as needing multiple perspectives and interdisciplinary interaction. To avoid research that offers "one solution fits all" -thinking. This can be seen in e.g. some technological fields."

"Yes definitely, but less in the sense that there are no solutions, but rather that we need many disciplinary and non-academic perspectives, knowledges and values."

"Recognizing wickedness also encourages humility, reflexivity, and iterative problem-solving—essential traits for addressing the challenges of sustainability in meaningful and context-sensitive ways."

Proposed item wording change

2.1 Systems thinking

Recognise Define **that** sustainability in research and innovation **involves complex, multi-faceted challenges, and therefore cannot be addressed through simplistic or one-dimensional solutions.** 'wicked problem' with multiple interdependent factors.

Original item

2.1 Systems thinking

Researchers and innovators should... recognize the influence of time, space and context on the sustainability of research and innovation activities.

<p>Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>
66,7	23,8	9,5
<p>Some respondents agreed fully to the item with the focus on contextualized and situated knowledge.</p> <p><i>"Attending to context leads to more accurate research."</i></p> <p><i>"Determination of time, space and context on the sustainability of research and innovation activities is essential for good projects."</i></p>	<p>Some respondents were neutral about the item because it was so broad to be considered not practically useful.</p> <p><i>" Not sure I can follow what this principle means, or what "recognise" would practically entail here... Is this about positionality or something?"</i></p>	<p>Two respondents similarly rejected the item for being too vague and unclear.</p> <p><i>"Too vague, broad, and general."</i></p> <p><i>"This is a bit unclear. Does this mean that when considering sustainability aspects in a research process, one should recognize the influence of time, space and context on the sustainability impacts. If yes, then it is ok as a competence."</i></p>

<p><i>"Yes, a concept such as "situated knowledge" (Haraway 1988)."</i></p> <p><i>"Not all things work in all environments! Local context is very important."</i></p> <p><i>"Sustainability isn't an abstract concept; it needs to be contextualized in relation to time, space, and in general to the specific characteristics of the context."</i></p> <p>One respondent also agreed with the item but emphasized that the aspects taken into account in paying attention to context could themselves be culturally influenced.</p> <p><i>"considering multiple forms and concepts around time and space could have cultural-based variabilities"</i></p>	<p><i>"This one doesn't mean much to me. Of course these are relevant but what does acknowledging that add?"</i></p> <p><i>"These are all important factors, although I think they are better known."</i></p> <p><i>"This item is not clear. Time, space and context is really broad and there is a lot of space for interpretation I find."</i></p>	
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Proposed item wording change

2.1 Systems thinking

Examine the sustainability of research and innovation activities in relation to recognize the influence of temporal, space **spatial** and contextual **factors**. on the sustainability of research and innovation activities.

Original item

<p>2.3 Problem framing</p> <p>Researchers and innovators should... engage multiple stakeholders from the outset and incorporate their perspectives and priorities on environmental issues.</p>

Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]	Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]	Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]
66,7	19,0	14,3
<p>Some respondents fully supported the items and the attention to different perspectives.</p> <p><i>"Again, I think it needs the perspective of all stakeholder to find systemic solutions."</i></p> <p><i>"We need to consider not only the priorities on environmental issues but also those on social and economic issues."</i></p>	<p>Some respondents were neutral about the item because a) there is not enough support/funding for researchers to do this; b) not all stakeholders can or should be engaged; c) the relevance of stakeholder engagement depends on the topic.</p> <p><i>"Not all stakeholders are equal when it comes to environmental issues.."</i></p>	<p>Similarly some respondents disagreed with the item because a) not all stakeholders can or should be engaged (particularly not those engaged in environmentally detrimental practices/industries) ; b) the relevance of stakeholder engagement depends on the topic.</p> <p><i>"I don't think every research project NEEDS to do this, e.g., a desk based review of conservation practices. I also don't think we ALWAYS need to incorporate stakeholder perspectives, although maybe we should CONSIDER them. Some</i></p>

Some respondents equated this with transdisciplinarity.

"Yes – transdisciplinarity"

"Because there are many different areas. That is why it is necessary to engage professors and experts from different fields - biology, hydrology, chemistry, physics - climate change scenarios, political science, etc."

One respondent emphasized the importance of paying particular attention to the perspectives of the most marginalized.

"Here, one should be careful not to practice extractivism of knowledge in research and innovation. When engaging stakeholders, particularly those from marginalized communities, it is essential to

"I agree with this, but researchers need MUCH more support in this area to do this effectively. Doing this right takes a lot of time and money. Forcing PAR on PhD students is often untenable. This should be institutionalized more than a simple virtue."

"Depending on the topic."

stakeholders will have un-sustainable perspectives and priorities (e.g., the executives of a coal mine). So it would depend on what you meant by INCORPORATE."

"This absolutely depends on context. If I'm working on a research project aiming to provide a policy roadmap for the phase-out of fossil fuels, I doubt it would be helpful to incorporate the perspective of fossil fuel producers on environmental issues. It could even derail the research project. In this sense, not all stakeholders should be given an equal space in the discussion when some have a greater responsibility in preventing positive change."

"This could be interpreted that for example in forest management research, the researchers should incorporate the priorities of forest owners into their research, even though their perspective would be contradictory to scientific understanding on how the forests should be managed? I think that all research should be justified through science, not through stakeholders' perspectives."

<p><i>facilitate space for these stakeholders as well as reciprocate—give something back to these communities beyond the product of our work.”</i></p> <p>Another agreed with the item, but wanted the types of stakeholders specified.</p> <p><i>“Yes, but maybe define or give examples of stakeholders.”</i></p> <p>Whereas another respondent that this would make research harder, but lead to better solutions.</p> <p><i>“This will bring in more complexity and be harder, but lead to better solutions.”</i></p>		
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Proposed item wording change

<p>2.3 Problem framing</p> <p>Engage multiple stakeholders – especially those most at risk of potential harms – from the outset and incorporate consider their knowledge, perspectives, and priorities to support more equitable outcomes.</p>

3. Envisioning Sustainable Futures

Original item

3.3 Exploratory thinking

Researchers and innovators should... plan every step of a research and innovation project with sustainability principles in mind, through a process of creative and systematic inquiry (for example using techniques from design thinking and ethics by design).

<p>Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>
66,7	23,8	9,5
<p>Some respondents agreed fully with the item.</p> <p><i>"Sustainability principles need to be always keep in mind and our actions need to be coherently related to them."</i></p>	<p>Some respondents were neutral about the item because they were unfamiliar with the suggested approaches or were not attached to the approaches.</p> <p><i>"I'm not familiar with these methods, but in principle I support this"</i></p>	<p>Similarly, some respondents disagreed with the item because they found the suggestion of specific approaches too perspective or did not like the approaches.</p> <p><i>"I think as soon as a recipe for design is created, the creativity declines. Establishment of commitments and principles may be more fruitful."</i></p>

"I love Design Thinking. I have introduced it as a separate subject."

"I think both principles are well suited to design a holistic research approach."

Some respondents agreed with this item, but emphasized that it would require the involvement of specific disciplinary experts (e.g. ethicists).

"In an ideal world, ethicists, and philosophers would be called upon and included in such endeavours. As an ethicist I would not claim that my maths can launch a rocket into space, I would equally be worried if design thinking and ethics by design methods were entrusted to technical policy experts and/or researchers from other fields with a

competence of having sustainability included in all steps of research."

"Perhaps - I think I would need more time to engage with whether I think those exact principles are good principles. But if they ARE good principles, then I agree with the way the statement is phrased. I think all researchers should engage with good ethical principles, and I think by extension good sustainability researchers should engage also with good sustainability principles. But I would need to look closer at whether the proposed framework ARE good sustainability principles."

"I'm not attached to the approach."

Some respondents were neutral about the item because they found

"The second part starting with "through" can be deleted. I like ethics by design. I don't like design thinking, as the definition doesn't seem obvious."

<p><i>low understanding of the moral implications of their work."</i></p> <p><i>"take into account that there are specific professions or occupations related to this competence"</i></p> <p><i>"Beside design thinking, new discipline is Methodology of Environmental Assessment. It is specified scientific interdisciplinary discipline, aiming to identify, predict and value environmental changes (biological, physical, chemical, social, economic and political). We mentioned it at our course Methodology of Political Science. Also, similar subject is Social Research Methods for Environment and Sustainability at University of Michigan, USA."</i></p> <p>One respondent agreed, but highlighted flaws in the ethics by</p>	<p>the suggestion of specific approaches too perspective</p> <p><i>"Too prescriptive."</i></p> <p><i>"If taken seriously, such a requirement would likely be counterproductive in its strictness."</i></p>	
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design approach re. asking the question if the technology is needed in the first place.

"Yes, but ethics by design itself sometimes lacks questioning whether we even need a certain technology before suggesting how to make that technology more ethically plausible."

Proposed item wording change

3.3 Exploratory thinking

plan every step of a research and innovation project with sustainability principles in mind, through a process of creative and systematic inquiry (for example using techniques from design thinking and ethics by design). Integrate sustainability principles throughout research and innovation processes drawing on systematic and creative forms of inquiry (for example, through an ethics by design approach)

4. Acting for sustainability

Original item

4.2 Collective action

Researchers and innovators should... participate in environmental and climate-positive initiatives within your research field.

Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]	Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]	Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]
61,9	28,6	9,5
<p>Some respondents agreed with the item, but either questioned whether this item referred to initiatives outside of the research role, or interpreted the item as referring to initiatives outside of the research role.</p> <p><i>"Do you mean, in addition to conducting your research?"</i></p>	<p>Another respondent was neutral to the item but interpreted the item as referring to changing a researcher's research focus to be environment and climate positive.</p> <p><i>"This depends. If a psychologist is researching schizophrenic disorders, and giving back to society in his own way in his research, there should not be an additional pressure to contribute</i></p>	<p>Other respondents disagreed, stating participation in positive initiatives is not for everyone.</p> <p><i>"Nobody should be forced to participate in initiatives they don't feel motivated to participate in. Maybe this could be just to be aware of such initiatives in own research field and consider participating, if appropriate?"</i></p>

<p><i>"This is important (in relation to environmental, socio and economical initiatives) in way to be a "virtuous model of behaviour" and to become "the change you want to see in the world", emphasizing coherence between the role as researcher and as citizen."</i></p> <p><i>"This provides researchers with practical experience and grounds their work in real-world contexts. Only by working on the ground and witnessing the challenges people face can researchers truly understand what kind of research is needed and the potential impact their work can have."</i></p> <p>Another agreed and gave an example from their own practice of how they do that.</p>	<p><i>to climate anxiety research/and/or initiatives which they may not be specialised in."</i></p> <p>Others were neutral about the item, considering participation in environmental and climate-positive initiatives as optional/or perhaps outside the role of the researcher.</p> <p><i>"If needed"</i></p> <p><i>"personal choices"</i></p>	<p><i>"I do not think this is necessary. It doesn't suit everyone's habitus."</i></p>
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<p><i>"As Associate Professor, I invite professors and researchers from my and from other fields - physics, management, chemistry,...and even art. After our artist [name and case example anonymized for publication], I invited him to present it to my master students."</i></p>		
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Proposed item wording change

<p>4.2 Collective action</p>
<p>Participate in Support environmental and climate-positive initiatives within your research field.</p>

Original item

4.3 Individual Initiative

Researchers and innovators should... appreciate how personal research goals can contribute to global sustainability objectives, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]	Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]	Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]
61,9	28,6	9,5
<p>Respondents who agreed with this item stated appreciation of the SDGs and how they can help to link individual practice to higher goals.</p> <p><i>"in my perspective this is fundamental in way to understand that SDGs are not theoretical goals far from our daily lives but they are influenced by our everyday behaviour and choices."</i></p>	<p>Two respondents were neutral about the item because they considered the SDGs use to be of limited added value in practice.</p> <p><i>"The SDGs are great, but invoking them does not necessarily lead to concrete action. There is also research pointing out they have been used extensively by corporations as a hollow communication tactic. Researchers and innovators should</i></p>	<p>One respondent who disagreed with the item considered the SDG too abstract to be useful for practice.</p> <p><i>"I love and know the SDGs, but I don't think they should be over-hyped. Often they are too abstract and distract from the goals rather than help us understand them."</i></p>

"This is a part of intrapersonal competence and inherently includes a self-awareness aspect: first one needs to recognise own goals and desires and only then it is possible to see how they align with the SDGs, and if they need to be adjusted.

"It is important to see the bigger picture in one's work and to know that you are not alone working on this."

"I like the SDGs"

"SDGs are currently an important frame, another one will come..."

One respondent further emphasized that all good research should do this.

"Agree, but don't think its specific to sustainability research. I think all good research should do this."

focus on the concrete benefit their project could create in people's lives both locally and globally."

"While can be a good indicator, this is often practiced as labeling."

<p>Whereas another gave an example of their contribution to the SDG goals in practice.</p> <p><i>"I am a member of the [example anonymized for publication] to implement SDG 4 in education system of UN member states."</i></p>		
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Proposed item wording change

<p>4.3 Individual Initiative</p> <p>Appreciate how personal research goals can align with social and environmental priorities, at both local and international levels. contribute to global initiatives such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).</p>

Original item

4.3 Individual Initiative

Researchers and innovators should... act as a green role model for other researchers and collaborators by applying sustainability competences in all areas of research and innovation including methodology, materials selection, and project goals.

<p>Agree or strongly agree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Neutral and respondent views and quotes [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>	<p>Disagree or strongly disagree [% and respondent views and quotes]</p>
<p>57,1</p>	<p>33,3</p>	<p>9,5</p>
<p>Some respondents agreed with the item and the power of role modelling.</p> <p><i>"It's important to lead by example rather than just give instructions—this is what truly motivates others to follow."</i></p> <p><i>"Good"</i></p>	<p>Some respondents were neutral to the item, considering it too much to ask researchers to be role models'.</p> <p><i>"Too much to ask... even to the most committed ones!"</i></p> <p><i>"In the social environment, this can go wrong very fast. It's better to have strict standards for evaluation than colleagues who aim to be an example for others or see it as a way to show off. It's our duty to serve society and</i></p>	<p>Another respondent disagreed that this was part of the role of a researcher.</p> <p><i>"Is this in their job-description? Are they paid for the additional work this entails? Creating a greater burden on researchers without giving them the tools to improve seems like an unfair strategy, especially when considering the much more financially rewarding careers they might have had outside of academia and/or research organisations."</i></p>

Others agreed with the item, but would remove the descriptive 'green'.

"Researchers and innovators should act as a role model for sustainability (non-only as a green role model) in each part of their activities"

"I would remove the word "green""

Still others agreed with the item and gave further examples of how researchers might achieve the competence.

"Especially to develop Methodology of Environmental Assessment in order to identify, predict and value environmental changes and also to improve implementation of models such as DPISIR, Life cycle assessment (LCA), or life cycle analysis, Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA)

the planet; fulfilling it doesn't make us better than others."

Another respondent did not feel the competence was informative.

"Yes, although I don't feel this statement is that revealing."

<p><i>model, which can be used for environmental standards to collect, analysis, assess, and reporting of data.</i></p> <p><i>"Asking the UNEP and the UNDP to monitor and assess in developing countries the projects and facilities"</i></p>		
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Proposed item wording change

<p>4.3 Individual Initiative</p> <p>act as a green role model for other researchers and collaborators by applying sustainability competences in all areas of Model sustainable practice in research and innovation including methodology, materials selection, and project goals.</p>

Section 3 - Demographics and teaching experience

Respondents were identified as coordinators of relevant courses across Europe from a systematic review of training programmes and materials. Twenty-one respondents participated in round 1 of the delphi (14% response rate).

Respondent characteristics

What is your gender?	n	%
Prefer not to say		
Woman	13	61,9
Man	6	28,6
Non-binary / non-conforming	1	4,8
Other [specify]	1	4,8

Which country (or countries) are you professionally affiliated with, or do you mainly work in? *	n	%
Austria	1	4,8
Belgium	1	4,8
Denmark	1	4,8
Finland	1	4,8
France	4	19,0
Germany	1	4,8
Hungary	1	4,8
Italia	1	4,8
Republic of Korea	1	4,8
Serbia	1	4,8
Slovenia	1	4,8
South Caucasus	1	4,8
Sweden	1	4,8
Taiwan	1	4,8
The Netherlands	3	14,3

United Kingdom	1	4,8
United States of America	2	4,8

*More than one country of work possible

Which of the following areas does your work mainly relate to? (Multiple selections possible)	n	%
Health; Culture and inclusive society; Civil security	4	19,0
Digital; Industry and space	4	19,0
Climate and mobility	8	38,1
Energy	2	9,5
Waters; Oceans	3	14,3
Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, environment; Soil; Natural resources	9	42,9
Other [please specify] *	11	52,4

*'Other' responses mostly reflected professional ethics, integrity and responsible conduct of research, and corporate responsibility courses.

Do you have experience training one (or more) of the following target groups?	n	%
Students	20	95,2
Early career researchers	18	85,7
Experienced researchers	11	52,4
Ethics reviewers, including Horizon Europe ethics appraisal scheme experts	0	0,0
Citizen scientists	3	14,3
Industry professional	8	38,1

References

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